

ULTRAVIOLET DEGRADATION OF POLYMER COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: Ultraviolet induced degradation has been examined to determine the nature and extent of resulting degradation mechanisms. Typical defects observed on naturally exposed laminates, e.g. matrix loss and cracking of the matrix, did not dominantly manifest on laminates sheltered from incident ultraviolet radiation in the natural environment. Accelerated ultraviolet exposure did not produce the typical forms of damage noticed on naturally exposed unprotected laminates. On these laminates, visible damage appears manifest at the surface. Surface damage observed on naturally exposed polymer composites was found to be dependent on the synergistic effect of degradation factors of ultraviolet radiation and moisture.

KEYWORDS: ultraviolet degradation, natural exposure, accelerated exposure, surface damage, epoxy laminates

INTRODUCTION

Unprotected polymer laminates experience degradation when exposed to the natural environment. This degradation may manifest visually as a colour change, cracking at the surface and exposure of reinforcing fibres at the surface. The damage in the laminate may be due to moisture diffusion, thermal cycling as a result of day/night cycles, and ultraviolet (UV) radiation. This damage appears to begin at the surface and progress toward the interior of the laminate. The damage at the surface is thought to be primarily due to the ultraviolet component of natural light.

Degradation of laminates result in a decrease in mechanical properties and consequently reduced load carrying capacity of a laminate. This reduction in strength may result in catastrophic failure if maintenance or precautionary measures are not timeously carried out. The rate of change of mechanical properties with time and / or operating hours is therefore required in order to determine when strength has been compromised. Using this information, maintenance and inspection routines may be optimised without a compromise in safety and this may result in reduce cost and downtime. The risk of failure of ageing polymer composite components can thus be reduced.

Moisture, temperature and ultraviolet radiation are generally accepted to be the common degradation factors to which laminates are exposed in the natural environment. Moisture can be typically in the form of humidity, condensation and rainfall. Diffusion of moisture into the matrix would result in plasticisation of the polymer matrix. Extensive work has been performed [1] characterising the diffusion of moisture into laminates and determining the effect on strength. Excess or fluctuating temperature is another environmental or operational factor that affects the performance of polymer composites. Service temperature of the

structure may be at ambient conditions, but the surface temperature may be well in excess of the ambient temperature approaching the glass transition temperature of the polymer. Although laminate temperatures experienced may be below the glass transition temperature, thermal cycling may induce damage both on the surface and at the interior of the laminate. Of the three degradation factors encountered in the natural environment, ultraviolet radiation damage is thought to be particularly damaging [2] to polymeric materials.

Degradation due to ultraviolet radiation may be studied by exposing the material to high intensity radiation in the wavelength of interest in an attempt to accelerate the degradation process. However such tests may unequally accelerate degradation mechanisms resulting in failure modes manifesting that would not otherwise occur.

Work has been undertaken [3] to combine the model of the various physical processes so that a comprehensive model can be established that would describe the degradation processes. However as yet no comprehensive model has been reported in the literature.

The effect of ultraviolet radiation on the surface of a laminate has been investigated by Lee *et al* [4]. From his investigations it was suggested that the photon energy in the short wavelength region, below 350nm, is strong enough to rupture most chemical bonds, example the C-C and C-H bonds, and as a consequence thereof produce radicals. The average value of ultraviolet light energy is greater than the binding energy of the hydrocarbon chain. From the review by White and Turnbull [5], it has been suggested that the creation of radicals in itself does not cause degradation of engineering properties as the long-chain nature of polymer molecules is preserved almost unchanged. Degradation has been attributed to the formed radicals being unstable and further undergoing scission reactions. Lee [4] has suggested that the radicals recombine with oxygen molecules in the air and used the results of an investigation to model degradation of electrical properties of fibre reinforced epoxy.

Signor *et al* [2] have observed that specific toughness and ultimate strain were the most sensitive to ultraviolet degradation after measuring a strain to failure decrease of approximately 40% and a decrease in specific toughness of approximately 60% on ultraviolet irradiated specimens. These values were measured after 4000 hours of irradiation in an integrating sphere based ultraviolet exposure chamber. The property changes have been attributed to embrittlement, or the creation of additional defects in a thin surface layer that would result in reduced energy for crack nucleation and propagation. Thus a decrease in bulk material properties may be as a result of a thin layer of degraded material at the surface.

Hardness and modulus tests performed on the same laminates by nano-indentation [2] showed an increase in hardness and modulus after 1000 hours of ultraviolet exposure, and subsequently no change after 4000 hours of exposure was observed. This suggested that after 1000 hours, or earlier, degradation has grown deeper than the average indentation depth of 80-90 μ m. Work reviewed by Signor [6] has revealed that degradation depths may reach depths greater than 100 μ m in short amounts of time. The increase in hardness and modulus is indicative of embrittlement and is consistent with observed changes in bulk tensile properties.

Natural exposure tests have been conducted incorporating sheltering of laminates from solar ultraviolet radiation with the aim of determining the effect of ultraviolet radiation on strength. The sheltering would allow moisture to be deposited on the laminate surface thereby allowing sheltered (protected) laminates to be exposed to the same levels of moisture as the unsheltered

(unprotected) laminates. The extent of degradation attributed to ultraviolet exposure can then be determined by comparing protected and unprotected laminates.

EXPERIMENTAL

Laminates were manufactured by hand lay-up using an epoxy matrix with woven 2×2 twill glass reinforcement. Ten layers of reinforcement were used to produce the laminates which upon release from the plate mould were post-cured as per manufacturers instructions. Specimens of dimension 150×50mm were cut from the sheets of laminates and secured to the exposure rack.

The exposure rack consists of a steel chassis with stainless backing and a cover that allows for framed exposure of individual laminates. Framed exposure was decided upon to eliminate edge effects by keeping the edge of laminates protected from the environment. The cover of the exposure frame contained cut-outs of approximately 130×40mm through which the specimens received exposure. The exposure racks were orientated at the latitude angle of the test site, as shown in Fig. 1, to maximise incident radiation onto the specimens.

Fig. 1: Exposure racks containing specimens at the latitude angle of the test site

Shading of laminates from natural ultraviolet radiation was performed by securing a shade cloth cover over a section of the exposure rack as illustrated in Fig. 1. The shade cloth cover manufactured by weaving polymer monofilaments is commercially available. The cloth has been independently tested [7] and found to protect sheltered objects from 97% of natural incident UV radiation.

RESULTS

Laminates protected by the shade cloth were compared to laminates that had no form of protection from the environment. This would enable the benefit of protection to be compared against unprotected laminate. Laminates that were stored in a dark environment at ambient

conditions, referred to as unexposed laminates were tested and the results provided a benchmark against which exposed laminates (both protected and unprotected) were compared. Observable changes on unprotected laminates were the loss of resin at the surface resulting in the exposure of the reinforcing fibre below after 10 months of exposure. In contrast, laminates protected by the shade cloth did not lose as much resin for a comparable exposure period as shown in Fig. 2. The change in surface texture is barely noticeable between the unexposed and protected surface laminate with the only change observable being the change in colour. The most significant change to the unprotected laminates were the loss of material from the surface resulting in the reinforcing fibres in the longitudinal weave becoming exposed. A colour change to the surface from white to yellow was also observed.

Fig. 2: Comparison of unexposed, protected and unprotected laminate surfaces after 10 months of exposure

The next inspection was performed after 15 months of exposure had been completed. At this stage reinforcing fibres on the surface of protected laminates remained barely covered by resin. Fibre tows below the surface could be observed through the thin transparent layer of resin. On the unprotected specimen surface, both the longitudinal and transverse tows were visible as appears in Fig. 3.

Changes in colour were discerned by observation without being quantified by use of a spectrophotometer. Colour on the protected surface changed to yellow from being originally white. On the unprotected surface, the resin that was visible between the fibre tows changed to a dark shade of yellow.

Fig. 3: Comparison of unexposed, protected and unprotected laminate surfaces after 14 months of exposure

Flexural strength measurements have been performed with the results appearing in Table 1 below. The values, as appears in the table below, are relative to unexposed values and is obtained by dividing the strength / modulus of the tested laminates by those of unexposed laminates which was regarded as the baseline against which all properties were compared. A relative flexural strength of 1.00 implies that no increase in strength of the laminate tested was recorded relative to that of unexposed laminates. A relative flexural strength less than 1.00 indicates a decrease in flexural strength and a value greater than 1.00 an increase in flexural strength.

Table 1: Comparison of flexural properties between protected and unprotected laminates

	Unprotected laminates	Protected laminates
Relative Strength	1.06	0.9
Relative Modulus	0.89	0.92

The strength of protected laminates appear to have been adversely affected in comparison to the unprotected laminates. A reduction in modulus was noticed on both protected and unprotected laminates.

DISCUSSION

An increasing loss of resin at the surface is evident with increasing exposure duration, especially in the case of unexposed laminates. The depth of resin loss for the specific case of unexposed laminates has been determined [8]. The rate of resin loss from the surface of protected laminates is less than that of the unprotected laminates as the reinforcing fibres on protected specimens remain protected after 14 months of exposure whereas after 10 months of exposure the reinforcing fibres on unprotected laminates were exposed to the environment. No damage was observed on the glass fibre reinforcement.

The rate of resin loss from the surface has resulted in both the transverse and longitudinal tows of the protected laminate being exposed to the environment after 14 months of exposure. The first layer of reinforcement, closest to the surface, is therefore assumed not to provide any contribution to strength of the specimen. On the protected specimens, the resin at the surface had been sufficiently worn away and / or material lost such that the reinforcing fibres closest to the surface were observed.

From visual observation, it was deduced that changes in colour were due to the intensity of ultraviolet degradation and above ambient temperature of the surface of the laminate. Protection by the shade cloth would result in the specimens being exposed to significant lower levels of radiation. The manufacturer of the shade cloth has also claimed that due to the weave on the shade cloth, not only is protection afforded from radiation, but surfaces protected by shade cloth experience lower temperatures than would be experienced by direct exposure to the sun due to flow of warm air through the cloth membrane.

From visual observation it would appear that the protected laminates have incurred much less damage than exposed laminates. Results from flexural tests however do not confirm this observation. In contrast, unprotected laminates appear to have experienced an increase in strength of 6% while the protected laminates experienced a decrease in strength of 10%. This would tend to suggest that while the laminates have been protected from ultraviolet exposure, other degradation mechanisms may have been accelerated. Both the protected and unprotected laminates experienced a reduction modulus of approximately 10% which is thought to be due to plasticisation of the matrix as a result of contact with moisture. Although the shade cloth shelters laminates from ultraviolet radiation, specimens would be exposed to moisture in the test environment.

Loss of matrix material from the surface of degraded laminates has been noted by Kumar *et al* [9] during examination of specimens that were subjected to both ultraviolet exposure and condensation. Kumar concluded that ultraviolet radiation and condensation operate synergistically to lead to extensive matrix erosion, matrix microcracking, fibre debonding and void formation. Although matrix dominated properties were most affected during the test period, it is expected that both fibre and matrix dominated properties will be affected over long exposure periods.

Sheltering of specimens from ultraviolet radiation does not appear to reduce the extent of strength reduction in naturally exposed laminates. This tends to suggest that although ultraviolet radiation and moisture may act synergistically and be the dominant degradation factors acting upon unprotected laminates, other degradation factors exist and the contribution to degradation become increasingly important in the absence of degradation due to ultraviolet radiation.

Exposure to continuous accelerated ultraviolet radiation exposure does not produce the same type of damage as that experienced by outdoor natural ultraviolet exposure [10]. A colour change of the surface resin was noticed but no cracking of the surface has been observed. Changes in mass were noted and no significant changes in compressive strength were measured. This observation would suggest that ultraviolet radiation alone does not result in surface cracking. Degradation reactions do however occur as evidenced by change in colour of the surface of the resin however these reactions may not be enough to influence the bulk material properties of the laminate.

Degradation induced damage appears to be limited to the surface and a gradient of properties may be set-up within the laminate as observed by Stratsev *et al* [11] when measuring the interlayer shear strength of polymer composites after long term ageing of laminates at the Black Sea coast. The surface of the laminates were found to be destroyed and disrupted to a greater extent than the subsurface layers. Analysis of laminates revealed that post-curing and destruction of the matrix occurred simultaneously.

CONCLUSION

The effect of environmentally induced ultraviolet radiation on polymer composites has been studied in an attempt to understand the degradation mechanisms initiated by exposure to naturally occurring ultraviolet radiation. By comparing laminates exposed to the natural environment against laminate sheltered from natural occurring ultraviolet radiation, it was noticed that the common degradation defects of resin loss leading to exposure of reinforcing fibres and matrix cracking near the surface are strongly dependent on incident ultraviolet radiation. In a natural environment, with reduced ultraviolet exposure, resin loss and matrix cracking did not occur to the same extent as would have otherwise occurred. During accelerated ageing of polymer composites, damage due to exposure to only ultraviolet exposure did not produce damage to the same extent when compared to that observed on laminates subjected to alternate cycling of ultraviolet radiation and moisture. Surface damage induced on polymer composites when exposed to the natural environment is therefore due to synergistic effects of ultraviolet radiation and moisture acting upon laminates.

REFERENCES

1. Springer G.S., "Environmental effects on composite materials, volume 2", Technomic Publishing, Lancaster, PA, 1981.
2. Signor, A.W., Van Landingham, M.R. and Chin, J.W., "Effects of ultraviolet radiation exposure on vinyl ester resins: characterization of chemical, physical and mechanical damage", *Polymer Degradation and Stability*, vol. 79 (2003), pp. 359-368.
3. McManus, H.L., Foch, B.J., and Cunningham, R.A., "Mechanism-based modelling of long-term degradation", *Journal of Composites Technology and Research*, vol. 22, no. 3, (2000), pp. 146-152.
4. Lee, B-S., Motoyama, T., Ichikawa K., Tabata, Y. and Lee, D-C., "The analysis of surface degradation on UV-treated epoxy/glass fiber by corona-charging properties", *Polymer degradation and stability*, vol. 66 (1999), pp. 271-278.
5. White J.R. and Turnbull A., "Review Weathering of polymers: mechanisms of degradation and stabilization, testing strategies and modelling", *Journal of materials science*, vol. 29 (1994), pp. 584-613.
6. Schoolenberg, G.E. and Vink, P., "Ultra-violet degradation of polypropylene: 1. Degradation profile and thickness of the embrittled surface layer", *Polymer*, issue 32 (1991), pp. 432-437.

7. <http://www.ultra-shade.com/uvprotection.shtml>, 28 March 2003.
8. Sookay N.K., von Klemperer C.J. and Verijenko V.E., "Environmental exposure of glass-fibre reinforced composites", International conference on computational & experimental engineering and sciences (ICCES), Madeira, Portugal, 26-29 July 2004, ICCES CD-ROM proceedings.
9. Kumar, B.G., Singh, R.P. and Nakamura, T., "Degradation of carbon fiber-reinforced epoxy composites by ultraviolet radiation and condensation", *Journal of composite materials*, vol. 36, no. 24 (2002), pp. 2713-2733.
10. Dlamini, P.M., "Accelerated environmental degradation of GRP composite materials", MSc thesis, submitted to Mechanical Engineering, University of KwaZulu-Natal, 2004, pp. 77-103.
11. Startsev, O.V., Krotov, A.S. and Statseva, L.T., "Interlayer shear strength of polymer composite materials during long term climatic ageing", *Polymer degradation and stability*, vol. 63 (1999), pp. 183-186.